

Fast smoothing on diamond surface by inductively coupled plasma

reactive ion etching

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Abstract: The synergistic effect of surface smoothing and quality optimisation of inductively coupled plasma reactive ion etching (ICP-RIE) on free-standing polycrystalline diamond (PCDs) was investigated. The results indicate that changing the reactive gas additives (Cl_2 , CHF_3 and CF_4) in primary O_2 plasma will lead to different diamond surface chemical states, correlated with different etching rates and surface morphologies. The uniform and smooth-etched PCD surface, of which the Root-Mean-Square (RMS) roughness is 2.36 nm with sporadic defects-etched pits and the average Ra roughness is 0.629 nm with standard-error of 0.057 nm in large area (500 μm), was obtained at a fast etching rate of 4.6 $\mu\text{m}/\text{min}$ via an optimum process involving the gas addition of CHF_3 at a flow ratio of 10% and radio-frequency (RF) power of 400 W, which combines the etching effect of H, F, O elements and ion bombardment enhancement. This optimal plasma process produced the highest bonding ratio of C-O-C/O-C=O associated with the smoothest surface after etching indicating that the symmetrical bond structure of C-O-C after surface oxidation reaction is related to the smooth diamond surface. This optimised approach was further introduced for the ultra-smooth surface (RMS down to 0.275 nm) etching of single-crystal diamonds (SCDs) with specific surface pattern at a fast etching rate of 0.23 $\mu\text{m}/\text{min}$.

Keywords: Chemical vapor deposition, Diamond, Reactive ion etching, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy, Raman spectroscopy

Introduction

Owing to its outstanding mechanical, electrical, chemical, and thermal properties, diamond is far superior to many other materials and is a very attractive functional material for special tools, optical devices, biosensors, quantum computation, potential microelectronics and microelectromechanical systems (MEMS), as well as the next-generation wide band-gap semiconductor electronic devices [1–4]. One of its most notable properties is stability, which enables diamond to remain stable even in harsh environments such as abrasion, radiation, chemical corrosion, high temperatures, and high voltage [2,5,6]. Such stability, however, makes the diamond extremely difficult to process using ordinary machining methods, which had hindered its wide range applications. With the development of science and technology, the higher-performance and smaller-scale diamond material is an absolute necessity for the advanced functional devices applications. In particular, the demand for diamond electronic and photonic devices has driven the international research community to focus on tunable diamond surface etching. As one of effective solutions, plasma etching technology has many advantages, including high etching rates, good selectivity, etching anisotropy, low linewidth ratios, surface accuracy and controllable etching, making it a key technique for realising microscale and nanoscale structures on diamond surfaces to facilitate the fabrication of diamond devices [6].

Reactive ion etching (RIE) is an effective method of plasma etching for the precision structuring of diamond films. Pure oxygen plasma has been used to produce diamond micro-mechanical components, whilst the majority of etching processes are based on oxygen plasma in combination with a secondary gas [7,8]. For example, Ar, SF₆, Cl₂, or CF₄ has been added to oxygen plasma to enhance the surface quality, although it can affect the etching rate and etching anisotropy [6,9-18]. However, for inductively coupled plasma (ICP)-RIE, it delivers higher etching rate because the plasma density is two orders of magnitudes higher than RIE. It has been previously

reported that the use of ICP allows the fabrication of smooth, homogeneously etched single-crystal diamond (SCD) surfaces [18-23]. Multiple parameters variation has been used to optimise the surface morphology and chemical reaction status of diamond during the ICP-RIE process [23]. So far, there are a number of reports on diamond nano-structuring and smoothing by ICP-RIE but there are few systematic studies of synergetic effect and optimisation of this etching method on diamond nor any accurate prediction of the etching results [6,24-25]. Thus, the investigation of the effect and refining of ICP-RIE multifarious parameters on diamond including both SCDs and PCDs is extremely important. This is particularly true for the diamond research community, especially for those wishing to develop diamond electronic and photonic devices requiring smooth diamond surfaces to form a perfect metallic electrode contact.

In the present work, the effect and optimisation of ICP-RIE process for surface fast smoothing on PCD samples under different gas system conditions were systematically studied. PCDs used here have diamond grain size of larger than 200 μm , allowing the effect of grain boundaries to be ignored (as each large grain can be considered as a small single diamond crystal in such a scale). The etching rate, etched surface quality, chemical effects of each added secondary gas were investigated in-depth, as well as the relationships between these factors. After the optimised etching parameters for PCD samples were obtained, these parameters were transferred to SCD samples, in order to verify the effectiveness of the process and realize the SCD surface patterning.

Results and Discussion

Gas chemical reaction on diamond

The etching effect in the gas plasma environment of ICP-RIE is based on the oxidizing reaction and ion bombardment mechanism [6,23,25]. The reaction on diamond in the gas system (pure O, O₂+CH₄, O₂+CHF₃, O₂+Cl₂) can be summarized into chemical equation as follow:

where the $C_{(diamond)}$ is the carbon element of etched diamond. When the additive gas amount increases and the RF power enhances, some conditions such as gas reaction and ion accumulation change. For example, with more CHF_3 addition, the overmuch H will react with F free radicals to form HF [8, 23]. That is, with the increase of H content, F free radical is constantly consumed, making the content of C in the plasma relatively increase, as shown in the reaction equation (7). At the same time, at the higher RF power, the increased C will exacerbate the amorphous carbon accumulation on the diamond surface as well as the superfluous C element of more C-contained gas (CF_4) addition as shown in equation (8,9), where $C_{(accumulated)}$ is the redundant C from gas source accumulated as amorphous carbon on the diamond surface at high RF power. Therefore, the surface morphology, surface quality and chemical state are strongly depending on the reaction and ion bombardment mechanism, which will be discussed in the subsequent parts.

Etching rate

Figure.1. Average etching rate of PCD samples in different conditions with diverse auxiliary gas (Cl_2 , CHF_3 , CF_4) and variable additive ratio (5%, 10%, 20%).

Figure.1 shows the average etching rate of the diamond samples in different conditions with diverse assisted gas types and variable additive ratio at RF power of 400W. Regarding the diamond etching in the pure O_2 , the etching rate is 2.6 $\mu\text{m}/\text{min}$, while when CHF_3 was added with the additive ratio from 5% to 10 %, the etching rate increased from 2.8 $\mu\text{m}/\text{min}$ to a maximum value of 4.6 $\mu\text{m}/\text{min}$. This is due to the increased number of ions bombarding the surface causing the stronger oxidation reaction compares with the etching condition with lower RF power in previous works [26]. However, further increasing the CHF_3 additive ratio to 20 %, the etching rate decreased. This is because more C ions were added simultaneously which facilitated the formation of CH_x and HF (Equation 8); the excessive C atoms weakened the oxidation reaction owing to the reduced reaction of CO or C, which affected the surface bombardment, as shown by equation (2) and (8) [6]. The presence of H ions caused the diamond etching rate to increase faster than that with most other assisted gas additions in O_2 . In the O_2+CF_4 gas system at the high RF power of 400 W, a diamond may be etched heavily if the moderate CF_4 gas ratio (10%) was used owing to the addition of F ions. However, the etching rate dropped as well when the CF_4 gas ratio increased to 20 %. This contrary etching effect was also due to the introduction of more C atoms. Meanwhile, the total speed declined to a minimum value of 0.8 $\mu\text{m}/\text{min}$ when 20 % of CF_4 gas ratio owing to the soaring of C elements accumulation on the diamond surface as shown in equation (9). Alternatively, when Cl_2 was added to O_2 , the etching effect on the diamond weakened when 10 % of Cl_2 was added. But it was

strengthened when the Cl_2 additive ratio increased to 20 %. The effect of Cl_2 acting as an assisted gas on the etching rate was not significant, and the etching rate under the O_2+Cl_2 conditions was nearly the same as that with pure O_2 etching. Continuously, the surface morphology of these samples will be used to demonstrate the correlations between each parameter.

Surface morphology

Figure.2. SEM images of a diamond etched in different gas systems at high RF power (400 W): a) PCD1, b) PCD3, c) PCD4, d) PCD6, e) PCD7, f) PCD9, and g) PCD10.

Figure.3. AFM images and large area surface profile of PCD6.

Figure 2 (a–g) shows the surface morphology of PCD samples etched in different gas systems at RF power of 400 W. As shown in Figure.2(c, e, g), corresponding to the PCD4, PCD7 and PCD10, which was etched in O₂ plasma with 20% Cl₂, CHF₃ and CF₄ added gas system, respectively, in each 1-μm² red square frame randomly marked region, the etched tiny pits of defects by ion bombardment were counted, allowing the statistical comparison of different processes for smooth surface etching at high RF power. Back to Figure.2(e), the average number of tiny pits of PCD10 was approximately 4; however, this value of PCD4 and PCD10 was 16 in Figure.2 (c) and 15 in Figure.2(g) respectively. At the same time, the calculated standard deviations were 55.6%, 13.3%, and 13.2%, respectively, indicating that the rough surface of PCD4 with larger uniformity. However, in Figure.2(e) some flat areas were formed in surface of PCD7, which was etched in the 20% CHF₃ added O₂ environment although it is uneven in large scale. It was theorised that ion bombardment could heavily damage the surface of the samples and weaken the selective etching if the RF bias power was enhanced. In Figure.2(a), the ion bombardment and reactive etching in pure O atmosphere resulted in an etched surface with circular indentations and several slow-etched parts (white particles). However, when 10 % of Cl₂ was added to O₂, in Figure.2(b), the potholes were smaller of PCD3. It was theorised that this effect may have been due to the catalytic action of Cl [6,25]. When more Cl₂ (20%) was added, however, the rounded potholes disappeared, and the entire diamond surface of PCD4 exhibited significant damage resembling hilly regions in Figure.2(c). This similar phenomenon also occurred in Figure.2(f, g) for PCD9 and

PCD10, where etching took place in a CF_4+O_2 atmosphere. It was due to the completely added oxidizing element of Cl (without C element), and, alternatively, more F elements in the etching environments compared to the condition of adding CHF_3 [6,25]. In Figure.2(e), the addition of 20% of CHF_3 in O_2 resulted in a significant reduction of tiny cavities and in the emergence of many small flat diamond surface areas. While for PCD6 in Figure.2(d) with 10% CHF_3 gas addition, a completely flat whole surface area was finally obtained. Correspondingly, as shown in Figure.3(a), the RMS roughness of PCD6 is 2.36 nm (although including some unavoidable sporadic defect-etched cavities) and in Figure.3(b) the average Ra roughness in large area of $500\ \mu\text{m}$ is merely 0.629 nm associate with standard-error of 0.057 nm, indicating the flat and uniform surface was obtained for PCD6. This improvement perhaps due to the appropriate additive amount of F and existing H element for sinking the pyramidal crystallites of surface roughness. The sporadic tiny cavities were resulted from the preferential etching of dislocations in the grains or the pores located at grain boundary of PCDs, which deposited with ultra-fast growth rate by recycle gas addition. These etched regions were more plicate or observed not apparently that co-existed with other etched areas in the rest of images. Therefore, the surface morphologies of PCDs at the condition of ion bombardment enhanced etching are cleaner and smoother with a faster etching rate compared with the results in Ref [26].

Quality of the diamond surface

Figure.4. Raman mapping and corresponding spectra of different surface areas, etched in O_2+Cl_2 (PCD4), O_2+CHF_3 (PCD7), O_2+CF_4 (PCD10) gas systems with an auxiliary gas flow ratio of 20 %, and pure O_2 (PCD1).

To understand the quality of diamond and quantify non-diamond phases, Raman spectroscopy was introduced, and it is extraordinary sensitive to the sp^2 carbon and amorphous carbon [27]. Figure.4 shows the Raman mapping and corresponding spectra of different areas of the diamond surface, which was etched in $O_2+20\% Cl_2$ (PCD4), $O_2+20\% CHF_3$ (PCD7), $O_2+20\% CF_4$ (PCD10), and pure O_2 (PCD1) gas systems. The dark, bright, and colour-transition regions in the mapping image of each sample were selected and tested. The spectrum background, which was related to the amorphous carbon that caused by heavy ion bombardment at high RF power on the diamond film, however, all appeared weaker than that of samples etched at low RF power in our previous works [26]. Moreover, a bulge in the position shown from 1430 cm^{-1} to 1580 cm^{-1} of the spectra could be probably attributed to the Raman active vibrational mode of sp^2 hybridized non-crystalline carbon on the etched surface [27,28]. As for the spectra of the diamond sample etched in O_2+CF_4 (PCD10), the bulge appeared more obvious, because of the accumulation of C on the surface and the contemporaneous slow etching rate [6,24]. However, owing to the inclusion of H atom in the CHF_3 , the broad peak of each Raman spectra on the diamond sample etched in O_2+CHF_3 (PCD7) almost disappeared, which resulted from the reaction as shown by equation (1). Likewise, all the spectra of the disparate regions of the PCD7 were nearly consistent with each other and the background was the lowest in these four samples. All these results show that the addition of the assisted gas CHF_3 to O_2 for etching at high RF power can realize a flatter diamond surface and suppress the accumulation of amorphous carbon, which is beneficial for realising not only high-speed etching but also smooth and refined surfaces.

Surface binding energy and chemical environment analysis

Figure.5. Deconvoluted C 1s XPS spectra of etched diamond samples in different gas systems with addition of 20 % auxiliary gas of a) PCD4, b) PCD7, c) PCD10, and pure O₂ etched d) PCD1.

Figure.6. Deconvoluted O 1s XPS spectra of etched diamond samples in different gas systems with addition of 20 % auxiliary gas of a) PCD4, b) PCD7, c) PCD10, and pure O₂ etched d) PCD1.

The surface composition after etching was changed, and this is related to the applied plasma. In the meantime, surface roughness of the sample is dependent on the applied etching process. Before fitting the curves, the spectrum results of XPS were calibrated by the adventitious carbon binding energy [29]. Figure.5 shows the

deconvoluted C 1s XPS spectra of diamond samples etched at RF power of 400 W with equal additions ratio of auxiliary gas in different gas systems. To study the effect of auxiliary gases on surface binding energy and chemical environments, which relates to the etching rate and surface morphology, we added marginally larger amounts (20 %) of auxiliary gases. The strong oxidisers (F and Cl elements) can promote O react with C of diamond. As shown in Figure.6, the addition of CF₄, CHF₃ and Cl₂ to O₂ upshifted the O-C bond strength from 531.5 eV of pure oxygen etched sample (PCD1) by 0.6, 0.6, and 0.7 eV, respectively; meanwhile, the O=C bond strength increased by 0.6, 0.6, and 0.8 eV from 532.7 eV of PCD1. Differently, in the Cl₂ added plasma environment, the etched diamond surface generated the O-Cl bonds located at 535.7 eV shown in Figure.6. However, in the case of inputting CF₄ and CHF₃, there is no O-F bonds produced as shown in Figure.6. Whilst CF₄ and CHF₃ were added as auxiliary gases, their influence on C-O and C=O was the same. In contrast, for the C 1s peak in Figure.5, the C-C binding energy changed from 284.4 eV of PCD1 to 284.5 (PCD10), 284.5 (PCD7), and 284.7 eV (PCD4), respectively; the C-O-C bond strength increased from 285.8 eV of PCD1 to 286.3 (PCD10), 286.4 (PCD4), and 286.4 eV (PCD4), respectively; and the O-C=O bond strength presented an increasing trend at first and then decreasing, i.e. from 287.2 eV of PCD1 to 287.6 (PCD10) and 287.8 (PCD7) and then down to 287.6 eV (PCD4) [30-32]. Theoretically, higher binding energy means stronger gas oxidisability (i.e. greater oxidation intensity and faster oxidation reaction). Moreover, notably, owing to the enhanced ion bombardment with strong oxidable medium, it is noted that there is no *sp*³ assignment in the C 1s XPS of all the etched diamond at higher RF power comparing with low RF power, which can be found in our previous works [26].

When the C-O/C=O ratio was related to the etching rate, C-O represented the main chemical bond type of reaction during surface etching. Once Cl was added, compared with pure O condition, in addition to the enhancement of C-O and C=O bond strength, the proportion of C-O also improved from 1.026 to 1.07 and the O-Cl was generated. In such cases, the C-O-C/O-C=O and C-O/C=O ratios resembled those of pure oxygen,

explaining why the etching rates in these examples were close to pure oxygen etching rates. The significant increase in C-O and C=O bond strengths in the O₂+Cl₂ etched sample was related to the synergetic effects of Cl, which also caused the etching rate to be higher than those of the CF₄ or CHF₃ etched samples with 20% addition of auxiliary gas, and formed rougher surface after etching.

The C 1s and O 1s deconvoluted XPS spectra demonstrated that there was no significant difference between the bonding reaction mechanisms when adding CF₄ and CHF₃, although the existence of H in the CHF₃ affected the diamond etching result (namely, it increased the bond strength of C-O-C and O-C=O as well as the C-O-C/C-O=C ratio). Theoretically, C-O-C is an equilibrium bond state, which, like diamond, oxygen terminates with O in the bridge position to connect to the C atoms of the diamond surface [33]. The achievement of the largest C-O-C/C-O=C ratio of 5.52 associated with the smoothest surface was obtained at the condition of adding 10 % CHF₃ into O₂ plasma under high RF power, comparing to those of the other conditions. In terms of the O 1s peak, the C-O/C=O ratios of 1.0 and 0.99 with the addition of CHF₃ and CF₄, respectively, were all less than 1.026 in pure O₂ and 1.07 in O₂+Cl₂ atmospheres. This phenomenon can prove the primary C-O etching reaction mechanism and agrees with the etching rate shown in Figure.1.

Figure.7. Deconvoluted Cl 1s XPS spectra of PCD4, and F 1s spectra of PCD7 and PCD10.

As shown in Figure.7, when CHF₃ or CF₄ was added to O₂, the F-C bond exhibited a simultaneous reaction with the oxidation reaction mechanism on diamond surface. O atoms in the discharge space can effectively prevent the recovery of CF₃ and CF₂ free radicals and promote the participation of more F free radicals in the etching process [6]. This is the reason why the C-O and the C=O binding energy did not change obviously, but the etching rate and the surface morphology exhibited a distinct difference. However, the higher concentrations of CHF₃ or CF₄ (20 %) that accumulated near the surface of the diamond were caused by ion bombardment at high RF power and promoted the formation of generated fluoride, as shown at 685 eV in the F 1s spectra in Figure.7 [34,35]. The H atoms in the CHF₃+O₂ system appeared to negatively affect the dissociation of the F free radicals compared with those of the CF₄ system. This phenomenon sometimes led to sharp reductions of the etching rate when 20 % of CHF₃ was added to O₂. Conversely, the synergetic effect of H in CHF₃ and O generated a specific etching effect on the diamond [36].

In summary, these results show that for realising a smooth surface of a diamond at high etching rates, the optimum gas addition is 10 % of CHF₃ into O₂ at an RF power of 400 W. Moreover, probably because the special etching effect of H on diamond and organic fluorine rarely accepted hydrogen bonds, the etching rate changed drastically if different amounts of CHF₃ were added under a 400 W bias power condition; however, F-C binding energy at 687.1 eV was the same as that of adding 20 % of CF₄ [35]. Likewise, although Cl can promote diamond oxidation, the formed chloride at high RF power will affect the surface reaction process, and, therefore resulted in a different surface morphology. Moreover, adding more fluorine-carbon (CHF₃ or CF₄) is adverse to the etching rate and surface smoothness, owing to the formation of fluoride, stronger oxidizing reaction and surface accumulation of carbon.

Optimised surface-smoothing etching process on SCD

Figure.8. 3D profile and 45° inclination of SEM images of etched SCD3 and SCD4 with different surface patterns: a) surface linear pattern; b) surface mosaic pattern.

Figure.9. AFM images and surface roughness of an ultra-smooth etched area of SCD3 and SCD4 with different surface patterns: a) surface linear pattern; b) surface mosaic pattern.

Normally, the SCD is the best choice for use in most high-performance diamond electronic devices, which makes SCD etching especially important. Depending on the investigation of the effect and optimisation of etching on a PCD with a large grain size, the optimised smoothing etching process is also feasible on SCD with different surface patterns. The ultra-smooth etched SCDs were obtained under this condition. Figure.8 shows the 3D profile and the 45° inclination of the SEM images of etched SCDs with linear and mosaic surface patterns. When etching in the 10 % CHF_3 added O_2 atmosphere at high RF power, the optimised process for SCD using the ultra-smooth surface was obtained at a high etching rate of $0.23 \mu\text{m}/\text{min}$. In Figure.9, as the AFM images and surface roughness measurements shown, the roughness of the smooth surface reached an RMS of 0.401 nm and 0.275 nm , respectively. In this figure, the uncovered areas of the high-pressure high-temperature (HPHT) diamond surface were flat and exhibited no disorder, whereas the side wall of the masked area was etched vertically without inclination. Meanwhile, as shown in the 3D images, distinct and consistent patterns were presented. The masked area exhibited a rugged surface

because the electron beam dissolved the aluminium layer that was too weak, amorphous and thin (100 nm) to protect the diamond from heavy ion bombardment [24]. As such, this area received uneven coverage under ion bombardment, negatively affecting the etching outcomes. At the same time, these parts acted as contrasting regions to the naked diamond surface where there was direct contact with the plasma. The oblique valley next to the masked area was the result of turbulent reactive ions caused by the extreme roughness of the region. This accelerated the reactive etching rate in local areas, as once the tiny pits and grooves formed, the areas underwent further etching at much faster speeds owing to the local high concentrations of accumulated reaction gases and ion bombardment [6,25]. Several pits of uniform round shape were the result of preferential etching and of the simultaneous ion bombardment of defects or impurities in HPHT diamonds where the quality was not as good as that of CVD epitaxial-grown SCDs. For the uncovered diamond area that had contact with the plasma and was subjected to ion bombardment, the ultra-smooth diamond surface was investigated at the nano scale by AFM. The multiple measured roughness of the flat surface except for the round-shaped pit regions reached an average RMS of 0.379 nm and the calculated standard deviation was 0.0745 nm, respectively, which were obtained from AFM scans performed 10 times over different unmasked areas of etched SCDs. To exclude the influence of deposited aluminium, we subsequently etched the naked back side of the SCDs under the same condition, and it likewise showed identical pits. These results indicate that high-performance diamond devices that require quick processing can be obtained by selecting high-quality CVD diamonds, thickening the mask layer and etching under optimum conditions. Depending on the ICP-RIE factors and investigation results obtained, diamonds with ultra-smooth surfaces and straight side walls can be achieved at fast processing speeds. This suggests that preparation technologies for complex and high-quality diamond devices and MEMS can be made even more precise at relative fast etching rate.

Conclusion

The synergetic effect of surface smoothing optimisation exhibited during the ICP etching of a free-standing PCD, prepared by DC arc plasma jet CVD, was investigated on the basis of diverse factors. The results of the study indicate that changing the additive assisted gas types generated different diamond surface oxidation states and chemical environments that resulted in different etching rates and surface morphologies. The chemical environment analysis performed that the observed ratio of C-O-C/O-C=O associated with the existence of a smooth surface. And the C-O was the main reaction bond mechanism during ICP-RIE etching for diamond smoothing. Depending on the factors present, optimal process for diamond smoothing were as follow: 10 % gas additions of CHF₃ in O₂ plasma at RF power of 400 W. Based on this, the smooth-etched diamond surfaces were realised at high etching rates. The ultra-smooth (average RMS roughness less than 0.5 nm) etched surfaces and contrast surface regions of the SCDs produced via the optimum process confirmed the mechanism and effectiveness of this optimised fast smoothing process.

Experimental Section

The diamonds used in this study were synthetic PCDs $5 \times 5 \times 1 \text{ mm}^3$ in size, cut with a laser from a 120-mm-diameter free-standing PCD wafer, which was prepared by a home-build 100 kW DC arc plasma jet chemical vapour deposition (CVD). This high-quality, free-standing PCD wafer was deposited for 200 h at a deposition speed of 7.5 $\mu\text{m/h}$ at 900–920 °C, with an input power of 30 kW and a chamber pressure of 3.1–3.2 kPa in an recycle Ar/CH₄/H₂ gas system. Samples were prepared by the following process: to guarantee the complete conformity of each sample (e.g. thickness, quality, and surface condition), we ground the entire wafer for 1 week by a precision lapping/polishing machine (UNIPOL-802). The smooth PCD wafer was then cut into 5×5 sample pieces. In addition, the same size surface-patterned commercially available HPHT Ib (100) SCDs were employed to observe ultra-smooth surface resulting from the optimized etching process, i.e., the procedure with optimum

parameters, which was obtained from the comparison of the etching results of PCDs. These PCD samples and the precisely polished SCDs were cleaned in boiling H_2SO_4 and HNO_3 mixed acids for 1 h and then ultrasonically cleaned in acetone and methanol for decontamination. Etched surface contrast patterns were realised by etching on the surface of the metal-masked SCDs, obtained through photoresist (SPR-955) development by using photolithography (SUSS-MA6) and covering the 100-nm-thick aluminium mask via electron beam evaporation at room temperature (Denton-Vacuum-Explore).

Diamond dry etching and temperature monitoring were carried out using an ICP-RIE etching system (SENTECH/SI-500). The constant inductance coil power of this system was 800 W, and the RF bias powers was 400 W (the temperature results of etching on diamond at 100 W were tested supplementally). The chamber pressure was maintained at 1 Pa by employing oxygen as the primary gas source at a flow rate of 100 sccm. Auxiliary gases (CF_4 , CHF_3 , or Cl_2) were added to 100 sccm O_2 at flow rates of 5, 10, and 20 sccm, respectively. Correspondingly, the addition ratio of assisted gas was 5%, 10% and 20% respectively. The details of the different etching conditions of the diamond samples and the produced effects are presented in Table I.

TABLE I. Diverse ICP processes and related etching rate of the diamond samples

No.	Gas flow ratio (%)	RF power (bias)	Etching time (min)	Etched thickness (μm)	Etching rate ($\mu m/min$)
PCD1	$O_2=100$	400	10	26	2.6
PCD2,3,4	$Cl_2/O_2=5,10,20$	400	10	24, 18, 30	2.4, 1.8, 3
PCD5,6,7	$CHF_3/O_2=5,10,20$	400	10	28, 46, 20	2.8, 4.6, 2
PCD8,9,10	$CF_4/O_2=5,10,20$	400	10	12, 16, 8	1.2, 1.6, 0.8
SCD1,2 (naked)	$CHF_3/O_2=10$	400	30	7.0 (7.1)	0.23
SCD3,4 (patterned)	$CHF_3/O_2=10$	400	30	-	-

PCD = polycrystalline diamond; SCD = single-crystal diamond;

The ratio is the flow of auxiliary gas divide by constant 100 sccm primary gas of O_2 .

A field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM, HITACHI S4800) and a laser scanning confocal microscope (LSCM OLYMPUS) were used to observe the surface morphologies. The etching rates of the samples were estimated using

ultra-precise profiler measurements (GUANGLU, accuracy is 0.0001mm) by testing the total thickness 20 times with a 1-mm-radius steel contact terminal at different positions of the PCD sample surface and non-masked side of SCDs before and after the etching to obtain its mean value. Here should be mentioned that the etching time for SCDs is 30 min, which was in order to realize surface pattern, thus the etching rate calculation was based on the etching time of 30 min on etched naked SCDs. The etching rate was in line with the time reported, and, thus, the average value could be calculated [11]. The diamond surface quality of the smoothly etched diamonds was demonstrated via visible Raman spectroscopy (NANOPHOTO, RAMAN-11) measurements with a 532-nm excitation wavelength. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS, ESCALAB 250Xi, Thermo Scientific) was used to characterise the surface binding energy and the chemical environment of the etching. The polished PCD surface and the ultra-smooth etched SCD surface were investigated by atomic force microscopy (AFM, ASYLUM RESEARCH HVA220) for multiple scanning. The grain size of PCD was captured using an optical microscope (OM OLYMPUS) in transmission mode.

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References

1. **J.R. Maze, P.L. Stanwix, J.S. Hodges, S. Hong, J.M. Taylor, P. Cappellaro, L. Jiang, M.V.G. Dutt, E. Togan, A.S. Zibrov, A. Yacoby, R.L. Walsworth and M.D. Lukin:** Nanoscale magnetic sensing with an individual electronic spin in diamond. *Nature* **455**, 644-647 (2008).

2. **Y.T. Zheng, J.L. Liu, J.J. Wang, Z.C. Li, H. Hao, J.J. Wei, L.X. Chen, H.T. Ye and C.M. Li:** The direct-current characteristics and surface repairing of a hydrogen-terminated free-standing polycrystalline diamond in aqueous solutions, *J. Phys. Chem. Solids.* **130**, 111-119 (2019).
3. **E.A. Ekimov, V.A. Sidorov, E.D. Bauer, N.N. Me'nik, N.J. Curro, J.D. Thompson and S.M. Stishov:** Superconductivity in diamond. *Nature* **428**, 542-545 (2002).
4. **J.L. Liu, K. An, L.X. Chen, J.J. Wei, W.Z. Tang, F.X. Lu, C.M. Li.** Progress of Freestanding CVD Diamond Films. *Surf. Tech.* **47**,1-10 (2018).
5. **R.S. Sussmann (Ed.):** CVD Diamond for Electronic Devices and Sensors. John Wiley & Sons, Chichester (2009).
6. **K. Nojiri (Ed.):** Dry etching technology for semiconductors. Springer (2012).
7. **Y. Tao and C.L. Degen:** Single-crystal diamond nanowire tips for ultrasensitive force microscopy. *Nano. Lett.* **15**, 7893–7897 (2015).
8. **Toros, M. Kiss, T. Graziosi, H. Sattari, P. Gallo and N. Quack:** Precision micro-mechanical components in single crystal diamond by deep reactive ion etching. *Microsyst. Nanoengin.* **4**, 12 (2018).
9. **J. Achard, A. Tallaire, V. Mille, M. Naamoun, O. Brinza, A. Boussadi, L. William and A. Gicquel:** Improvement of dislocation density in thick CVD single crystal diamond films by coupling H₂/O₂ plasma etching and chemo mechanical or ICP treatment of HPHT substrates. *Phys. Status. Solidi. A.* **212**, 2264–2267 (2014).
10. **M. P. Hiscocks, C.J. Kaalund, F. Ladouceur, L. François, S.T. Huntington, B.C. Gibson, S. Trpkovski, D. Simpson, L.A. Eric, P. Steven and B.E. James:** Reactive ion etching of waveguide structures in diamond. *Diam. Relat. Mater.* **17**, 1831-1834 (2008).
11. **T. Izak, A. Kromka, O. Babchenko, M. Ledinsky, K. Hruska and E. Verveniotis:** Comparative study on dry etching of polycrystalline diamond thin films. *Vacuum* **86**, 799-802 (2012).

12. **S. Kunuku, K.J. Sankaran, C. Tsai, W. Chang, N. Tai, K. Leou and I.N. Lin:** Investigations on Diamond Nanostructuring of Different Morphologies by the Reactive-Ion Etching Process and Their Potential Applications. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*. **5**, 7439–7449 (2013).
13. **P. Leech, G. Reeves and A. Holland:** Reactive ion etching of diamond in CF₄, O₂, O₂ and Ar-based mixtures. *J. Mater. Sci.* **14**, 3453–3459 (2001).
14. **H. Shiomi:** Reactive ion etching of diamond in O₂ and CF₄ plasma, and fabrication of porous diamond for field emitter cathodes. *Jpn. J. Appl. Phys.* **36**, 7745 (1997).
15. **Dorsch, M. Werner and E. Obermeier:** Dry etching of undoped and boron doped polycrystalline diamond films. *Diam. Relat. Mater.* **4**, 456–459 (1995).
16. **Y. Ando, Y. Nishibayashi, K. Kobashi, T. Hirao and K. Oura:** Smooth and high-rate reactive ion etching of diamond. *Diam. Relat. Mater.* **11**, 824–827 (2002).
17. **J. Schmitt, W. Nelissen, U. Wallrabe and F. Völklein:** Implementation of smooth nanocrystalline diamond microstructures by combining reactive ion etching and ion beam etching. *Diam. Relat. Mater.* **79**, 164–172 (2017).
18. **C.L. Lee, E. Gu, M.D. Dawson, I. Friel and G.A. Scarsbrook,** Etching and micro-optics fabrication in diamond using chlorine-based inductively coupled plasma. *Diam. Relat. Mater.* **17**, 1292-1296 (2008).
19. **T. Yamada, H. Yoshikawa, H. Uetsuka, K. Somu, T. Norio and S. S. Ichi:** Cycle of two-step etching process using ICP for diamond MEMS applications. *Diam. Relat. Mater.* **16**, 996–999 (2007).
20. **P. Forsberg and M. Karlsson:** High aspect ratio optical gratings in diamond. *Diam. Relat. Mater.* **34**, 19-24 (2013).
21. **A.B. Muchnikov, A.L. Vikharev, J.E. Butler, V.V. Chernov, V.A. Isaev. S.A. Bogdanov, A.I. Okhapkin, P.A. Yunin and Y.N. Drozdov,** Homoepitaxial growth of CVD diamond after ICP pretreatment. *Phys. Status. Solidi.* **212**, 2572–2577 (2015).

22. **H. Uetsuka, T. Yamada and S. Shikata:** ICP etching of polycrystalline diamonds: Fabrication of diamond nano-tips for AFM cantilevers. *Diam. Relat. Mater.* **17**, 728–731 (2008).
23. **Z. Cui (Ed.):** Micro-Nanofabrication Technologies and Applications. Higher Education Press (2009).
24. **S. Castelletto, L. Rosa, J. Blackledge, M. Zaher, A. Abri and A. Boretti:** Advances in diamond nanofabrication for ultrasensitive devices. *Microsyst. Nanoengin.* **3**, 17061 (2017).
25. **M.J. Jackson and W. Ahmed (Eds.):** Micro and Nano-manufacturing, volume II. Springer (2018).
26. **Y.T Zheng, H.T Ye, J.L Liu, J.J Wei, L.X Chen, C.M Li:** Surface morphology evolution for polycrystalline diamond by inductively coupled plasma reactive ion etching (ICP-RIE). *Mater. Lett.* **253**, 276-280 (2019).
27. **S. Iqbal, M.S.Rafique, S.Akhtar, N. Liaqat, N. Iqbal and R. Ahma:** A comparative study on finding an effective root for the introduction of hydrogen into micro plasma during diamond growth. *J. Phys. Chem. Solid.* **122**, 72-86 (2018).
28. **Dychalska, K. Fabisiak, K. Paprocki, M. Jarosław, I. Aizhan and S. Mirosław:** A Raman spectroscopy study of the effect of thermal treatment on structural and photoluminescence properties of CVD diamond films. *Mater. Design.* **15**, 320-327 (2016).
29. **B.V. Crist:** XPS in industry—Problems with binding energies in journals and binding energy databases. *J. Electron Spectrosc. Relat. Phenom.* **231**, 75-87 (2019).
30. **M. Varga, T. Izak, V. Vretenar, H. Kozak, J. Holovsky, A. Artemenko, M. Hulman, V. Skakalova, D.S. Lee and A. Kromka:** Diamond/carbon nanotube composites: Raman, FTIR and XPS spectroscopic studies. *Carbon* **111**, 54-61 (2017).
31. **X.Y. Pan, L.J. Wang, Q.K. Zeng, L.Y. Shi, R. Xu, J. Huang, K. Tang and**

- Y.B. Xia:** XPS study of polycrystalline diamond surfaces after annealing treatment. *Surf. Coat. Tech.* **228**, S446-448 (2013).
32. **J. Birrell, J. Gerbi, O. Auciello, J. Gibson, D. Gruen and J. Carlisle:** Bonding structure in nitrogen doped ultrananocrystalline diamond. *J. Appl. Phys.* **93**, 5606-5612 (2003).
33. **M.M. Hassan and K. Larsson:** Effect of surface termination on diamond (100) surface electrochemistry. *J. Phys. Chem. C.* **118**, 22995–23002 (2014).
34. **A. Tressaud, F. Moguet, S. Flandrois, M. Chambon, C. Guimon, G. Nanse, E. Papirer, V. Gupta and O.P. Bahl:** On the nature of C-F bonds in various fluorinated carbon materials: XPS and TEM investigations, *J. Phys. Chem. Solids.* **57**, 745-751 (1996).
35. **J.D. Dunitz and R. Taylor:** Organic fluorine hardly ever accepts hydrogen bonds. *Chem. Eur. J.* **3**, 89-98 (1997).
36. **B. Sun, X. Zhang, Q. Zhang and Z. Lin:** Effect of atomic hydrogen and oxygen on diamond growth. *J. Appl. Phys.* **73**, 4614-4617 (1993).